

WebAssembly benefits and application scenarios at CERN

AUGUST 2024

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

WebAssembly (often abbreviated to WASM) allows developers to write code in languages like C, C++, or Rust and compile it into a platform-independent binary format¹.

Support for WebAssembly in the cloud native ecosystem is a growing trend with multiple existing open source projects. WASM offers a powerful combination of cross-language compatibility, portability, and performance. This project will focus on evaluating the existing WASM ecosystem and projects and experimenting with a runtime for Kubernetes nodes at CERN, covering both self managed and OpenShift/PaaS deployments.

¹ <https://webassembly.org/>

ABSTRACT

This report explores the benefits and potential uses of WebAssembly (Wasm) at CERN. WebAssembly is a technology that allows code written in various programming languages to run efficiently and securely on different platforms, including web browsers, servers, and edge devices. Initially designed to improve web applications' performance, Wasm is now being considered for broader applications at CERN, such as real-time data processing on edge devices and GPU-accelerated tasks.

The report discusses the evolution of WebAssembly, highlighting its advantages like fast execution, security, and cross-platform compatibility. It also compares different Wasm runtimes and their integration into containerized environments, which is relevant for deploying Wasm at scale.

The report also covers practical aspects of using WebAssembly in a Kubernetes cluster. It provides a guide for setting up runwasi with containerd or configure crun properly to deploy WebAssembly applications.

Additionally, the report compares WebAssembly runtimes like Wasmtime, Wasmedge, and Wasmer, and briefly discusses WasmCloud, a platform for distributed Wasm applications that can integrate with Kubernetes.

Challenges noted include the current limitations of WebAssembly features and language support. Despite these, WebAssembly shows great promise for certain applications. It is not yet a complete replacement for traditional container runtimes in every situation, particularly for performance-critical tasks. However, its advantages in terms of portability, quick startup times, and security make it a valuable tool for specific use cases at CERN.

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INTRODUCTION

In the paper that formally introduced the world to WebAssembly, the authors indicate that the motivation was about rising to meet the needs of modern, web-delivered software in ways that JavaScript alone could not². The goal was to provide software that is safe, fast, portable and compact. These attributes are crucial for the performance and security demands of today's diverse and distributed computing environments.

In order to provide software's portability, we need to consider two main issues: software is dependent on APIs (such as OpenGL, POSIX or Win32) that are not platform-agnostic. The second main issue is that software is going to run on different hosts, with diverse hardware and security capabilities.

Until now, JavaScript has been the only way to solve these problems since it is ubiquitous, portable and provides some sense of security when run in a sandboxed environment. Unfortunately, there is a difference between JavaScript code running as a client compared to running it on a server. Its single-threaded design complicates long-running tasks or highly concurrent ones and due to its origins as a dynamic language, there are several classes of optimizations that are unavailable as options to even the fastest and most modern JavaScript runtimes.

NaCl

It was for these and other reasons that Google began to consider an alternative approach to safe, fast, and portable client-side web development. In 2011, Google released a new open source project called Native Client (NaCl). The idea was to provide near-native speed execution of code in the browser while running in a limited privilege sandbox for safety reasons³.

The technology was successful in the sense that the performance demonstrated in the browser was only minimally off of native execution speeds. The problem was that the NaCl binaries would need to be generated and maintained for each target platform and would only run in Chrome. They also ran in an out-of-process space, so they could not directly interact with other Web APIs or JavaScript code.

NaCl deserves a tremendous amount of credit for moving the industry in this direction, but it was ultimately too fiddly and too Chrome-specific to carry the open web forward.

asm.js

Mozilla's attempt focused on a subset of JavaScript that could be optimized ahead-of-time (AOT). Utilizing the LLVM-based clang frontend parser via the Emscripten toolchain, compiled C and C++ code could be efficiently converted into this JavaScript subset, making it portable and reasonably performant.

However, the resulting file was significantly larger than its native counterpart due to the need to include standard library functions and browser-specific hooks, highlighting the difference between portable code and portable applications.

Despite its limitations in performance compared to Google's NaCl/PNaCl, asm.js demonstrated the feasibility of deploying C and C++ applications in browsers with minimal code changes. It served as a

² Andreas Haas, Andreas Rossberg, Derek L. Schuff, Ben L. Titzer, Michael Holman, Dan Gohman, Luke Wagner, Alon Zakai, and JF Bastien. Bringing the web up to speed with webassembly. SIGPLAN Not., 52(6):185–200, jun 2017

³ Brian Sletten. WebAssembly: The Definitive Guide. O'Reilly Media, 2021.

significant stepping-stone, showing that optimized, sandboxed JavaScript code could be generated from various languages using LLVM-based toolchains.

WebAssembly

Developers across the web ecosystem recognized the need for a high-performance, sandboxed, and portable code solution that worked within existing web infrastructure. This culminated in the initiation of WebAssembly in 2015, led by Brendan Eich, the creator of JavaScript. WebAssembly was conceived as a "binary syntax for low-level safe code"⁴ that could initially work with asm.js but eventually evolve to support multiple programming languages at a low level.

WebAssembly (abbreviated Wasm) is a binary instruction format for a stack-based virtual machine. Wasm is designed as a portable compilation target for programming languages, enabling deployment on the web for client and server applications. You can take code written in over 30 different languages and compile it into a .wasm file, and then can execute that file in the browser, on a server, or even on a car.

Despite a running joke in the WebAssembly community that WebAssembly is “neither web nor assembly,” the name conveniently suggests its functionality. WebAssembly serves as a target platform with a set of instructions that resemble assembly language. The fact that WebAssembly modules are frequently going to be delivered over the web as another type of URL-addressable resource justifies the inclusion of the word Web in the name.

⁴ Brendan Eich. From asm.js to webassembly. <https://brendaneich.com/2015/06/from-asm-js-to-webassembly/>, 2015. Accessed: 2024-07-04.

WASM Benefits

WebAssembly excels because of the following five characteristics⁵:

- **Portable:** The binary format for Wasm bytecode is standardized, meaning that any runtime capable of executing Wasm will be able to run any Wasm code. This is similar to Java's promise of "write once, run anywhere".
- **Universal:** Many languages can compile into Wasm. This support goes beyond systems languages like C, C++, and Rust to include garbage-collected, high-level languages like Go, Python, and Ruby. A full list of languages that compile to Wasm can be found [here](#).
- **"Near-Native Performance":** Wasm is often described as having "near-native performance". What this actually means is that WebAssembly is almost always faster than JavaScript, especially for compute-intensive workloads, and averages between 1.45 and 1.55 times slower than native code⁶, but results do vary by runtime⁷.
- **Fast Startup Time:** The cold start time of Wasm is important enough that it warrants a category of its own. On the server, it can achieve 10-100x faster cold starts than Docker containers⁸ because it does not need to create a new OS process for every container. In the browser, decoding Wasm and translating it to machine code is faster than parsing, interpreting, and optimizing JavaScript, and so Wasm code can begin executing at peak performance more quickly than JavaScript can.
- **Secure:** WebAssembly was designed with the web in mind and so security was a priority. Code running in a Wasm runtime is memory sandboxed and capability constrained, meaning that it is restricted to doing what it is explicitly allowed to do. While sandboxed, Wasm code can still be granted access to the underlying system, including system-level interfaces and hardware features.

WebAssembly APIs

The evolution of WebAssembly extended further with the introduction of the WebAssembly System Interface (WASI). WASI is a standard that provides WebAssembly with the ability to perform system-level operations, such as file and network access, in a secure and portable manner. By defining a set of system calls that are platform-independent, WASI enables WebAssembly applications to run outside the browser in various environments, including servers, IoT devices, and more. This extends the applicability of WebAssembly beyond the web, making it a versatile tool for developers across different domains⁹. This is the isolation mechanism used by the CRUN runtime when running WebAssembly applications on a Kubernetes cluster.

Thanks to APIs like WebGPU and WebNN, WebAssembly can now also serve as a platform for GPU or NPU accelerated workloads, breaking its previous limitation to CPU workloads, such as those typically handled by the Java Virtual Machine (JVM). WebGPU and WebNN allow developers to write generic code capable of running on any hardware without depending on vendor-specific APIs like CUDA. This cross-hardware compatibility offers significant advantages, since it makes it possible to have the same container image running machine learning workloads being able to run on any kind of node, without being restricted to the GPU vendor or the CPU architecture.

⁵ Harshal Sheth. Pay attention to WebAssembly. <https://harshal.sheth.io/2022/01/31/webassembly.html>. Accessed 2024-08-08.

⁶ Abhinav Jangda et al. Not So Fast: Analyzing the Performance of WebAssembly vs. Native Code. USENIX ATC 19, jul 2029.

⁷ Frank Denis. Performance of webassembly runtimes in 2023. <https://00f.net/2023/01/04/webassembly-benchmark-2023/>. Accessed: 2024-07-10.

⁸ Gackstatter, P. (2021). A WebAssembly container runtime for serverless edge computing [Diploma Thesis, Technische Universität Wien]. repository. <https://doi.org/10.34726/hss.2021.85181>.

⁹ Wasi api docs. <https://wasi.dev/>. Accessed: 2024-07-08.

WebAssembly Use Cases

Originally designed to enable high-performance web applications, WebAssembly has evolved to become a versatile technology with a wide range of practical use cases¹⁰. In this section, we explore the practical applications of WebAssembly and how it is revolutionizing the way the web is built and experienced.

FaaS/Serverless Platforms

Function-as-a-service platforms need to execute user-provided code quickly and safely. Since serverless platforms are often used to run code for short durations, startup times are a particularly important metric. The ultra-fast cold starts and broad language support make Wasm a good choice for serverless workloads¹¹.

The CDN-edge computing platforms provided by Cloudflare Workers¹² and Fastly Compute@Edge¹³ already provide the ability to run WebAssembly. Fastly claims 100x faster startup times than other offerings in the market, and attributes this speedup to their WebAssembly-based compiler and runtime.

Embedded Sandboxing

The idea of embedding WebAssembly within other applications is useful beyond plugin systems. In fact, it can be used to sandbox entire third-party libraries or to construct layers of security for first-party code.

Firefox is leading the way¹⁴ in this area by protecting itself against bugs in third-party libraries, like the ones they use for spell checking or image decoding. In conjunction with a tool called RLBox, which provides a tainting layer, they can protect against vulnerabilities in those libraries without resorting to heavy-handed process isolation.

High-Performance Web Applications

WebAssembly allows developers to execute code at near-native speed in the browser, bridging the performance gap between web and desktop applications. By compiling high-level languages like C, C++, and Rust to Wasm, developers can achieve significant speed improvements for computationally intensive tasks, making complex applications run seamlessly in the browser.

To give an idea, let's suppose we want to perform matrix multiplication efficiently on the browser¹⁵. We can do it by writing some simple code in C.

¹⁰ Webassembly docs - use cases. <https://webassembly.org/docs/use-cases/>. Accessed: 2024-07-05.

¹¹ It's worth noting that there are other alternatives. AWS Lambda, for example, uses the lightweight [Firecracker MicroVM](#). In a head-to-head, WebAssembly does have some [performance advantages](#).

¹² Cloudflare docs - webassembly (wasm). <https://developers.cloudflare.com/workers/runtime-apis/webassembly/>. Accessed: 2024-07-05.

¹³ MJ Jones. How Compute is tackling the most frustrating aspects of serverless. <https://www.fastly.com/blog/how-compute-edge-is-tackling-the-most-frustrating-aspects-of-serverless/>. Accessed 2024-08-08.

¹⁴ Bobby Holley. WebAssembly and Back Again: Fine-Grained Sandboxing in Firefox 95. <https://hacks.mozilla.org/2021/12/webassembly-and-back-again-fine-grained-sandboxing-in-firefox-95/>. Accessed 2024-08-08.

¹⁵ Trung Le. Unleashing the power of webassembly — practical use cases for a seamless web experience. <https://link.medium.com/g7SKWfyOYKb>, 2024. Accessed: 2024-07-05.


```
// matrix_multiply.c
#include <stddef.h>

void matrix_mul(int* a, int* b, int* result, int rows, int cols, int dim) {
    for (int i = 0; i < rows; ++i) {
        for (int j = 0; j < cols; ++j) {
            int sum = 0;
            for (int k = 0; k < dim; ++k) {
                sum += a[i * dim + k] * b[k * cols + j];
            }
            result[i * cols + j] = sum;
        }
    }
}
```

We now need to compile it to WebAssembly using the Emscripten toolchain (LLVM backend for WASM).

```
emcc -O3 -s WASM=1 -o matrix_multiply.wasm matrix_multiply.c
```

And finally integrate the code in our JavaScript application, that will just handle the output management.

```
fetch('matrix_multiply.wasm')
  .then((response) => response.arrayBuffer())
  .then((bytes) => WebAssembly.instantiate(bytes, {}))
  .then((results) => {
    const instance = results.instance
    const matrixA = new Int32Array([1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6])
    const matrixB = new Int32Array([7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12])
    const resultMatrix = new Int32Array(matrixA.length)
    instance.exports.matrix_mul(
      matrixA.byteOffset,
      matrixB.byteOffset,
      resultMatrix.byteOffset,
      2,
      2,
      3
    )
    console.log(resultMatrix)
  })
```

Machine Learning in the Browser

WebAssembly is opening new frontiers for running machine learning models directly in the browser, enabling on-device inference without relying on external servers. This approach enhances user privacy by processing sensitive data locally, providing a smoother and more responsive experience for machine learning applications¹⁶. This is also followed by the effort of defining a web-friendly neural network APIs, that acts as an abstraction layer to machine learning capabilities of underlying hardware¹⁷.

Let's see an example that uses TensorFlow.js with the WebAssembly backend to load a pre-trained machine learning model and perform inference in the browser¹⁸.

¹⁶ Web-llm in-browser inference engine. <https://github.com/mlc-ai/web-llm>. Accessed: 2024-07-08.

¹⁷ Web neural network api. <https://www.w3.org/TR/webnn/>. Accessed: 2024-07-08.

¹⁸ Trung Le. Unleashing the power of webassembly — practical use cases for a seamless web experience. <https://link.medium.com/g7SKWfyQYKb>, 2024. Accessed: 2024-07-05.


```
import * as tf from '@tensorflow/tfjs'
import '@tensorflow/tfjs-backend-wasm' // WebAssembly backend

async function runModel() {
  // wasm backend uses webGL, a new backend using webGPU is in development
  await tf.setBackend('wasm')

  // Load the model
  const model = await tf.loadLayersModel('path/to/model.json')

  // Generate dummy input tensor
  const inputTensor = tf.tensor2d([[1, 2, 3, 4]], [1, 4])

  // Model inference
  const result = model.predict(inputTensor)

  // Display the result
  result.print()
}

runModel()
```

Porting Legacy Applications

WebAssembly also serves as a bridge for porting legacy applications to the web. Applications written in languages such as C, C++, or Rust can be compiled to WebAssembly, making it easier to bring existing software to the browser without a complete rewrite. Support for programming languages that require garbage collectors (C#, Java, Golang) is in an active development stage, with various degree of stability¹⁹. Some early stage projects also focus on bringing support to interpreted languages, enabling popular languages like Python to be run on browsers²⁰.

Cross-Platform Development

WebAssembly's platform-independent nature enables developers to write code in any language, compile it to WASM, and run it on any platform that supports WASM execution. This cross-platform compatibility enables code reuse and simplifies the development process, as the same WASM module can be utilized across different environments, be it web browsers, servers, or edge devices.

Gaming

The gaming industry is another area where WebAssembly has made substantial inroads. Modern web games demand high performance and responsiveness, which traditional JavaScript often struggles to deliver. New generation game engines²¹ leverage WebAssembly to enable developers to compile their games for the web, allowing complex 3D games to run smoothly in the browser.

Potential use cases at CERN

Edge devices

CERN's experiments generate vast amounts of data that require real-time processing at the edge, close to where the data is produced. Edge devices at CERN need to be powerful enough to handle

¹⁹ Blazor. <https://dotnet.microsoft.com/en-us/apps/aspnet/web-apps/blazor>. Accessed: 2024-07-08.

²⁰ Pyscript. <https://pyscript.net/>. Accessed: 2024-07-08.

²¹ Ambient - game engine docs. <https://ambient.run/docs/introduction>. Accessed: 2024-07-08.

complex tasks but also flexible and secure. WebAssembly provides an efficient solution for deploying code to these edge devices due to its lightweight nature and fast execution. Since WebAssembly is platform-agnostic, it allows CERN to deploy the same code across various types of edge hardware without the need for extensive reconfiguration. This uniformity not only simplifies the deployment process but also ensures that the code runs efficiently and securely, even on resource-constrained devices.

GPU workloads

CERN's research often requires the use of GPU-accelerated computing to process large-scale simulations and analyze massive datasets. As of now, these workloads are handled through platform specific APIs, WebAssembly can be explored as a means to optimize and simplify GPU-based tasks. By compiling software to WebAssembly, CERN can create highly portable GPU workloads that can be executed across different platforms, including those that may not natively support the required GPU architecture.

WebAssembly's ability to interact with GPU APIs such as WebGPU or WebNN opens up new possibilities for distributed and collaborative research, where researchers can share and run GPU-accelerated tasks in a more accessible and standardized manner. The portability and security of WebAssembly further ensure that these workloads can be deployed confidently across a variety of computing environments without compromising on performance or safety.

Container Runtimes Compared

When running WebAssembly modules through high-level container runtimes, there are two options. We can still depend on low-level runtimes (like *crun*) to call the WASM runtime, or we can configure containerd to interact directly with them. Using this approach shortens the invocation path. This is handled by containerd leveraging the *runwasi* project, which enables developing a containerd-wasm-shim that interacts directly with the WASM runtime.

Runwasi does not and is not meant to have better performance than *crun*. Instead, it's an attempt to leave runtime execution to a wide variety of runtimes and application hosts built with them. It is important to state that as of July 2024, runwasi is still in an alpha state and should not be used in production²².

²² Runwasi project. <https://github.com/containerd/runwasi>. Accessed: 2024-07-10.

As *runwasi* enables system administrators to choose WASM runtimes, comparing them becomes crucial. In this section we want to highlight the differences between them, shining a light on the advantages they provide. Since numerous runtimes are available²³, we had to select the best-maintained and popular ones at the time of writing.

It is essential to note that each runtime offers APIs to integrate WebAssembly applications into existing programming languages. This is what we call the *language support* of the runtime. It is crucial to take this into account when choosing a WASM runtime if we plan to write WebAssembly modules that enable us to gently transition to WASM.

Wasmtime

Wasmtime specializes in executing WebAssembly modules in a secure and efficient manner. It offers a just-in-time (JIT) compilation strategy, which optimizes the execution speed by compiling the WASM code at runtime. Wasmtime is written in Rust and provides bindings for various programming languages. It is developed by the Bytecode Alliance.

Wasmedge

Wasmedge focuses on providing a high-performance and extensible environment for executing WASM modules²⁴. Wasmedge boasts a modular architecture that allows developers to customize and extend the runtime according to their specific needs. It is the runtime used by *crun* and is developed by CNCF (Cloud Native Computing Foundation).

Wasmer

Wasmer is a standalone WebAssembly runtime that provides a universal runtime environment for executing WASM modules. It allows running WASM code anywhere, from servers to edge devices,

²³ Wasm runtimes list. <https://github.com/appcypher/awesome-wasm-runtimes>. Accessed: 2024-07-10.

²⁴ Ashish Singh. Comparing webassembly runtimes. <http://link.medium.com/hEdf0Ukx7Kb>. Accessed: 2024-07-10.

with a focus on performance and portability. Wasmer supports multiple programming languages and provides a rich set of APIs for embedding into existing applications.

Wasmer aims for fast startup times and low runtime overhead, and according to independent testing it should be the fastest among the three²⁵.

Integrating WebAssembly

In this section, we'll go through the setup steps required to enable WebAssembly on a Kubernetes cluster. CRUN is a low level container runtime to which high level runtimes, like containerd, connect in order to run containers. We will show how to enable WebAssembly on CRUN, making it able to call a WASM runtime, like WasmEdge.

This adds a level of indirection that can lead to slower startup times. This is why we will show how to set up runwasi as well. As explained previously, runwasi enables containerd to call a WebAssembly runtime directly. This removes a layer in the architecture, thus theoretically improving performance. It is really important to state again that, as of the time of writing, runwasi is still in alpha state and should not be used in production.

Using CRUN

In order to enable CRUN to execute a WebAssembly workload, we will have to make sure that CRUN has the WASM flags already enabled. Performing `crun -v` on a node in the cluster, we can notice the `+WASM:wasmedge` flag. This states that WebAssembly runtimes are supported by the CRUN runtime, requiring only configuration on the higher level runtime (in this case `containerd`, but `cri-o` also supports it).

```
crun version 1.14.4
commit: a220ca661ce078f2c37b38c92e66cf66c012d9c1
rundir: /run/user/1000/crun
spec: 1.0.0
+SYSTEMD +SELINUX +APPARMOR +CAP +SECCOMP +EBPF +CRIU +LIBKRUN +WASM:wasmedge
```

In order to enable WASM on a node we just need to append the following configuration to `/etc/containerd/config.toml` and restart containerd, using `systemctl restart containerd`.

```
[plugins."io.containerd.grpc.v1.cri".containerd.runtimes.crun]
  runtime_type = "io.containerd.runc.v2"
  pod_annotations = ["module.wasm.image/variant"]
[plugins."io.containerd.grpc.v1.cri".containerd.runtimes.crun.options]
  BinaryName = "crun"
[plugins."io.containerd.grpc.v1.cri".containerd]
  default_runtime_name = "crun"
```

In order to automate this change, an HELM chart is [made available](#). Alternatively, the following script can be used to enable WebAssembly on all the nodes of the cluster, when run from a node with access to the cluster. Use with caution and read it thoroughly to be sure it does not perform changes you don't want to be made.

```
#!/bin/bash
```

²⁵ Frank Denis. Performance of webassembly runtimes in 2023. <https://00f.net/2023/01/04/webassembly-benchmark-2023/>. Accessed: 2024-07-10.


```
# The text to be added to the config file
TEXT='version = 2
root = \"/var/lib/containerd\"

[plugins]
  [plugins.\"io.containerd.grpc.v1.cri\"]
    sandbox_image = \"registry.cern.ch/kubernetes/pause:3.2\"

[plugins.\"io.containerd.grpc.v1.cri\".containerd.runtimes.crun]
  runtime_type = \"io.containerd.runc.v2\"
  pod_annotations = [\"module.wasm.image/variant\"]
[plugins.\"io.containerd.grpc.v1.cri\".containerd.runtimes.crun.options]
  BinaryName = \"crun\"
[plugins.\"io.containerd.grpc.v1.cri\".containerd]
  default_runtime_name = \"crun\"
,

# Fetch the list of node names
nodes=$(kubectl get node -o name --no-headers | sed -e 's|node/||')

# Loop through each node and execute the SSH command
for node in $nodes; do
  ssh -o \"StrictHostKeyChecking no\" core@${node}.cern.ch \"sudo su -c \
    'echo \"$TEXT\" > /etc/containerd/config.toml \
    && systemctl restart containerd'\" &
done

# Wait for all background processes to finish
wait

echo \"Configuration update and containerd restart completed on all nodes.\"
```

Using runwasi

In order to enable runwasi on a Kubernetes cluster running containerd, you can follow the guide [we wrote](#). We will now go through the main steps.

We will compile runwasi, but binaries are also made available by the maintainers. To make this process easier, we wrote a GitLab CI pipeline that can be [triggered manually](#) to fetch the latest version from the official repository and compile it. Binaries are made available as artifacts of the pipeline itself.

In order to install the binaries, we need to execute the `setup.py` script on a server that has access to the cluster. This script copies the compiled software in `/usr/local/bin/` and appends the following configuration to `/etc/containerd/config.toml`.

```
[plugins.\"io.containerd.grpc.v1.cri\".containerd.runtimes.wasmtime]
  runtime_type = \"io.containerd.wasmtime.v1\"
[plugins.\"io.containerd.grpc.v1.cri\".containerd.runtimes.wasmedge]
  runtime_type = \"io.containerd.wasmedge.v1\"
[plugins.\"io.containerd.grpc.v1.cri\".containerd.runtimes.wasmer]
  runtime_type = \"io.containerd.wasmer.v1\"
```


Runtime verification

Test deployment

In order to verify the correct configuration of WebAssembly with CRUN, we deploy the following demo application. Save this file to `deployment.yaml` and run it in your cluster using `kubectl apply -f deployment.yaml`. Feel free to edit this deployment as desired.

```
apiVersion: apps/v1
kind: Deployment
metadata:
  name: wasm-deployment
  labels:
    app: wasm-test
spec:
  replicas: 4
  selector:
    matchLabels:
      app: wasm-test
  template:
    metadata:
      labels:
        app: wasm-test
      annotations:
        module.wasm.image/variant: compat-smart
    spec:
      containers:
      - name: wasm-test
        image: wasmedge/example-wasi-http
        ports:
        - containerPort: 1234
```

In order to run WebAssembly workloads on *crun* we need to add an annotation to Pods (`module.wasm.image/variant: compat-smart`) in order to instruct *crun* itself that containers in the Pod might need a WASM runtime to be executed. Alternatively, we can set a logical link called *crun-wasm* that points to *crun* as our runtime. This is equivalent to using the annotation `module.wasm.image/variant: compat` that executes all workloads as WASM ones by default. This will make newly instantiated linux containers not run on the cluster.

We can verify the status of the running Pods with the appropriate command (`kubectl get pods -o wide`). We can also test the application by forwarding the appropriate port and fetching the demo webpage.

```
kubectl port-forward deployment/wasm-deployment 8080:1234
curl localhost:8080
```

CRUN

We want to verify that CRUN is actually running the containers in the nodes. In order to do it, we need to log in on a node in the cluster that is running a Pod related to the previously specified deployment. We can get the container ID of the running deployment by querying the running containers using `sudo crictl ps -a`. We can then look into the `runtimeType` field of that container using `sudo crictl inspect CONTAINERID | grep "runtimeType"`.

On our systems, we get that the `runtimeType` is `io.containerd.runc.v2`. This is a *shim* that calls CRUN in order to execute containers on the node.

runwasi

Using runwasi we can get rid of the annotation, since we are not using CRUN. This is the deployment that we can apply to our cluster, once runwasi is installed.

```
apiVersion: apps/v1
kind: Deployment
metadata:
  name: wasm-deployment
  labels:
    app: wasm-test
spec:
  replicas: 4
  selector:
    matchLabels:
      app: wasm-test
  template:
    metadata:
      labels:
        app: wasm-test
    spec:
      containers:
        - name: wasm-test
          image: wasmedge/example-wasi-http
          ports:
            - containerPort: 1234
```

In order to verify that the correct runtime is being used, we can replicate the steps specified in the previous section. A low level WASM runtime should be set as the *runtimeType*, like `io.containerd.wasmedge.v1`.

When running linux containers runwasi will default to [youki](#), a low level runtime written in Rust²⁶. This makes runwasi be able to execute both types of workloads, but unfortunately it cannot be changed with `crun` or `runc`. Also, since `youki` is embedded in the runwasi binary, it will not show up using `strace`.

Double-checking using strace

We can verify which runtimes are actually being called by looking at the system calls made by `containerd`. We can do it by performing `sudo strace -f -p "pidof containerd" -o stracelog` and looking at the `execve` in the strace file. For instance, we get the following when applying our deployment using the CRUN runtime.

```
8140 execve("/usr/bin/crun", ["crun", "--root", "/run/containerd/runc/k8s.io",
  "--log", "/run/containerd/io.containerd.ru...", "--log-format", "json",
  "create", "--bundle", "/run/containerd/io.containerd.ru...", "--pid-file",
  "/run/containerd/io.containerd.ru...", "6645bdee3357eecd5772b9d57d0b0cea"...],
0xc0001e8700 /* 13 vars */) = 0
```

On the other hand, this is what we get when using runwasi with wasmedge.

```
7131 execve("/usr/local/bin/containerd-shim-wasmedge-v1",
["/usr/local/bin/containerd-shim-w"... , "-namespace", "k8s.io",
  "-address", "/run/containerd/containerd.sock", "-publish-binary",
  "/var/usr/local/bin/containerd", "-id", "94f00e035351fc03dd358968ab2d911b"... ,
  "start"], 0xc001986300 /* 14 vars */ <unfinished ...>
```

²⁶ Unfortunately, this is not documented. You can find the relevant piece of code here: <https://github.com/containerd/runwasi/blob/4e0e396bd117f5c0b90a90025abc9842beaa941e/crates/containerd-shim-wasm/src/sys/unix/container/executor.rs#L45-L68>

Node selection with RuntimeClass

We can also enable WebAssembly or runwasi only on certain nodes in the cluster. We can label nodes accordingly using a predefined label. In the following example we use the label `runtime=runwasi`.

```
kubectl label nodes NODE runtime=runwasi
```

We can use the following RuntimeClass to enable the Pods to be scheduled only on those nodes. RuntimeClasses are a feature for selecting the container runtime configuration for running pods within the same cluster. By specifying a RuntimeClass in a pod's configuration, we can select which container runtime handler will be used to run that specific pod²⁷.

```
apiVersion: node.k8s.io/v1
kind: RuntimeClass
metadata:
  name: wasmedge
scheduling:
  nodeSelector:
    runtime: runwasi
handler: wasmedge
```

Another option is to not define a `nodeSelector`, thus enabling us to select the runtime that is going to run the workload without imposing node restrictions.

```
apiVersion: node.k8s.io/v1
kind: RuntimeClass
metadata:
  name: wasmedge
handler: wasmedge
```

WasmCloud

[WasmCloud](#) is another approach to running WebAssembly workloads. Unlike other `crun` and `runwasi`, WasmCloud is a platform specifically designed for building distributed, actor-based applications.

WasmCloud actors are the smallest deployable unit and they handle messages delivered to them by the host runtime via capability providers. Actors can also invoke exposed functions of capability providers which have been explicitly assigned to them.

Capability providers on the other hand represent code which is not part of the core business logic, such as an HTTP server, or a message broker. While actors are compiled to WebAssembly, this is not required for capability providers²⁸.

WasmCloud includes lattice, a self-forming, self-healing mesh network using NATS that provides a unified, flattened topology. It integrates well with Kubernetes, but does not depend on it. It can be set up natively, but as of now the recommended way to run it is in a pod on a cluster.

When considering whether to deploy WasmCloud, it is crucial to consider if the actual performance benefits are worth the switch to a new platform. It is true that it integrates well with Kubernetes, but

²⁷ Runtimeclass documentation. <https://kubernetes.io/docs/concepts/containers/runtime-class/>. Accessed: 2024-07-23.

²⁸ Kjorveziroski, Vojdan, Sonja Filiposka, and Anastas Mishev. "Evaluating webassembly for orchestrated deployment of serverless functions." 2022 30th Telecommunications Forum (TELFOR). IEEE, 2022.

transitioning or integrating it cannot be hassle free. As of the time of writing, WasmCloud does not support some of the tools that populate the Kubernetes ecosystem, like Istio²⁹.

Moreover, WasmCloud represents a different paradigm of deploying applications that may require training and time to adapt to. We argue that an accurate assessment of the actual benefits of moving to this new technology is needed, so that they can be counterweighted by the cost of transitioning itself. This complexity has the potential to be relevant for an organization like CERN.

Setting it up

Pre-requisites

Before proceeding with the installation, we had to enable the required CSI drivers on our test cluster³⁰. This might not be necessary on every cluster, based on the storage one might want to use. It is done by adding the following arguments when creating the cluster through openstack:

```
--merge-labels --labels cinder_csi_enabled=True.
```

Installation

We followed the instructions [provided](#) by the WasmCloud team. You can find the version we used at the time of writing [here](#).

When installing NATS we had to set the StorageClass manually, since our cluster does not provide a default one. This can be easily done by overwriting the value when installing the [NATS helm chart](#). To do that, just use the following command instead of the one provided in the instructions.

```
helm install my-release-name path/to/chart \
                                     --set
config.jetstream.fileStore.pvc.storageClassName="STORAGE_CLASS" \
--set config.resolver.pvc.storageClassName="STORAGE_CLASS"
```

Alternatively, we can also set the default StorageClass for the entire cluster, using the following command.

```
kubectl annotate storageclass STORAGE_CLASS
storageclass.kubernetes.io/is-default-class="true"
```

Deploying an application

We created a small [demo project](#) to test the cluster setup with WasmCloud. This demo serves as a simple example to ensure everything is working correctly and can act as a baseline for building more complex, production-ready applications in the future. By starting with this demo, developers can easily expand and adapt it to meet the needs of more sophisticated projects. Instructions can be found in the project's "Readme" file.

²⁹ Here you can find the list of integrations officially supported by WasmCloud. <https://wasmcloud.com/docs/integrations/>.

³⁰ Kubernetes @ CERN Storage Docs. <https://kubernetes.docs.cern.ch/docs/storage/>. Accessed 2024-08-08.

Rough edges we found along the way

As we integrated WebAssembly into our workflows, we encountered a few challenges that highlighted some rough edges in the technology. Based on our expertise, these are not deal breakers and should be fixed in the years to follow.

Work in progress

WebAssembly is still a relatively young technology, and many of its features are under active development. This means that certain functionalities, like threading support or advanced debugging tools, are still maturing³¹. For instance, multi-threading in WebAssembly is possible, but it requires specific configurations and can be complex to implement correctly. These limitations can sometimes slow down development or necessitate workarounds that add complexity to projects. While the WebAssembly ecosystem is evolving rapidly, developers need to be aware that they might encounter unfinished or experimental features that could impact their workflows.

Actual language compatibility

WebAssembly supports a broad range of programming languages, but the level of maturity and stability varies significantly across them. While languages like C, C++, and Rust have robust support and produce highly optimized WASM code, others like Java, C#, and Python are still catching up³². The tooling for these languages might not yet provide the same level of performance, and certain language-specific features may not be fully supported. For instance, we found the support for Java to be very premature and not suited for a production ready project. This inconsistency can be a hurdle for teams looking to port existing applications or libraries to WebAssembly, as they might face limitations or need to rely on less mature tools, which can introduce bugs or inefficiencies.

"Near" native performance

WebAssembly is often praised for its "near-native" performance, but in practice, there are scenarios where this claim doesn't hold up. While WebAssembly can achieve impressive speeds, it doesn't always match the performance of native code. As we highlighted previously, it is almost always faster than JavaScript, especially for compute-intensive workloads, and averages between 1.45 and 1.55 times slower than native code³³. Additionally, the lack of direct access to hardware features (like SIMD) in some environments can limit the potential performance gains.

For tasks where performance is critical and the overhead introduced by WebAssembly becomes noticeable, traditional containerization technologies like Docker may still be preferred. Containers offer near-native performance and greater control over the execution environment, making them better suited for workloads that demand the highest levels of efficiency.

Performance Analysis

Several studies and benchmarks have been conducted to compare the performance of WASM runtimes, both in general contexts and within containerized environments like Kubernetes. In this

³¹ WASM proposals list. <https://github.com/WebAssembly/proposals>. Accessed 2024-08-08.

³² WASM programming languages support list. <https://github.com/appcypher/awesome-wasm-langs>. Accessed 2024-08-08.

³³ Abhinav Jangda et al. Not So Fast: Analyzing the Performance of WebAssembly vs. Native Code. USENIX ATC 19, jul 2029.

section, we'll delve into the performance implications of running WebAssembly workloads on Kubernetes.

Execution modes

A Wasm module can typically be run in one of three compilation modes: Interpreter, Just-In-Time (JIT), or Ahead-of-Time (AOT)³⁴. The decision depends on the user's preference for resource usage, execution speed, etc.

- AOT, which facilitates quick startup, exceptionally small footprint, and results in almost native speed.
- Interpreter, which offers small memory usage, little footprint, and comparatively slow.
- JIT, it allows to run WASM at almost native speed while maintaining a platform-neutral distribution. However, compilation might be expensive during runtime.

Standalone performance

In an earlier investigation, Jangda et al. attempt to understand the efficiency of Wasm binaries³⁵. However, this study is focused solely on web browsers and does not provide sufficient insights into standalone runtimes. Another study by Wen and Weber introduces an operating system designed to run WASM applications in edge environments, comparing their results to native Linux execution³⁶. They report improved execution speed over native code while retaining the security advantages of WASM.

Building on this, Wang addresses the limitations of prior studies by offering a more comprehensive evaluation of standard WASM runtimes³⁷. This research examines the five most widely-used independent WASM runtimes. The study also introduces a new benchmark suite, WABench, which includes tools from established benchmarks along with complete applications from various domains.

The goal is to assess the performance efficiency of standalone Wasm runtimes. Wang explores the impact of JIT compilers, AOT compilation, and Wasm compiler optimizations on performance. The findings indicate that wasmtime, wavm, and wasmer, which utilize JIT compilation, outperform wasm3 and wamr, which rely on interpretation.

Overall, compared to the native execution, the five standalone WebAssembly runtimes introduce an average performance slowdown of 1.67× (Wasmtime), 3.54× (WAVM), 1.59× (Wasmer), 6.99× (Wasm3), and 9.57× (WAMR), respectively.

This work serves as a baseline for performance analysis due to its integration of a broad range of benchmarks, though it is limited to x86-based architectures and lacks multi-architecture support.

In summary, the paper notes the following: the performance degradation of interpretation-based runtimes is consistent across both short- and long-running benchmarks. The Cranelift JIT demonstrates promising results in the JetStream, MiBench, and PolyBench benchmark suites. In all

³⁴ Kakati and Brorsson, "WebAssembly Beyond the Web." in 2023 3rd International Conference on Intelligent Technologies (CONIT), pp. 1-8, 2023.

³⁵ Abhinav Jangda et al. Not So Fast: Analyzing the Performance of WebAssembly vs. Native Code. USENIX ATC 19, jul 2029.

³⁶ E. Wen and G. Weber, "Wasmachine: Bring the edge up to speed with a webassembly os," in 2020 IEEE 13th International Conference on Cloud Computing (CLOUD), pp. 353–360, IEEE, 2020.

³⁷ W. Wang, "How far we've come—a characterization study of standalone webassembly runtimes," in 2022 IEEE International Symposium on Workload Characterization (IISWC), pp. 228–241, IEEE, 2022.

benchmarks, WAVM exhibits higher memory usage, and in general, WASM runtimes consume more memory than native applications.

Spies and Mock examine the performance and usability of WASM in three non-web environments: desktop, server, and IoT devices³⁸. The authors conclude that Wasm has potential for use in non-web environments, especially in resource-constrained settings where it offers a lightweight alternative to native code.

Cold start evaluation

Comparative analysis of performance differences in terms of the initial start up delay between traditional Docker containers and WebAssembly modules has been done by Long et al.³⁹, finding that WASM starts up 10 times faster than the same workload running in a containerized environment.

Kjorveziroski et al.⁴⁰ compares the cold start latency and execution speed of WebAssembly modules to that of containers in cases where the WebAssembly runtime is integrated with the interface of a container runtime. This is done by analyzing the cold start delays and total execution times of three WebAssembly runtimes: WasmEdge, Wasmer, and Wasmtime to the performance of the containerd container runtime, using distroless and distro-oriented container images.

The research also introduces a new benchmarking suite⁴¹ comprised of 13 different sequential applications, representing both the functionality of common serverless functions as well as more theoretical microbenchmarks. Each benchmarking function has been evaluated with all runtimes using both JIT and AOT compilation. Results are compared to distroless and distro-oriented container images.

The results indicate that WebAssembly runtimes generally exhibit superior execution times in most tests (10 out of 13), when comparing WASM AOT execution to the performance of distroless and distro-based container images.

³⁸ B. Spies and M. Mock, "An evaluation of webassembly in non-web environments," in 2021 XLVII Latin American Computing Conference (CLEI), pp. 1–10, IEEE, 2021.

³⁹ Long, J., Tai, H.-Y., Hsieh, S.-T., Yuan, M.J.: A lightweight design for serverless function-as-a-service. IEEE Software vol.38(1), pp. 75–80(2021). <https://doi.org/10.1109/MS.2020.3028991> arXiv:2010.07115 [cs] (2019)

⁴⁰ Kjorveziroski and Filiposka, "WebAssembly as an Enabler for Next Generation Serverless Computing." in Journal of Grid Computing, pp. 34, 2023.

⁴¹ WASM Serverless Benchmarks. <https://github.com/korvoj/wasm-serverless-benchmarks>

Average execution time using AOT compilation, in seconds

However, for sustained compute performance in complex tasks like image processing or matrix multiplication, additional improvements are necessary for WebAssembly runtimes. In contrast, container runtimes currently deliver better performance due to their higher compute capabilities, though they suffer from cold start issues. The potential impact of multi-threading support on WebAssembly performance is still uncertain and will only be clarified once it becomes a stable feature.

When analyzing JIT compilation, Wasmtime demonstrated the best performance in 8 out of the 13 cases. However, it is important to note that WasmEdge was not included in the JIT comparison due to its reliance on interpretation rather than true JIT compilation. Additionally, Wasmer was excluded from several tests that require I/O access to the underlying filesystem. Indeed, even though Wasmer does support WASI, it was not possible to execute these functions with crun's WebAssembly integration, limiting its participation in the benchmarking. Distroless and distro-oriented container images, included in the comparison, do not use JIT compilation, thus serving as a static performance baseline for comparison.

Among the three WebAssembly runtimes analyzed, Wasmtime, when integrated with containerd, provided the best performance in 8 out of the 13 cases. WasmEdge followed, excelling in 4 cases, while Wasmer led in just one test. When considering JIT compilation, Wasmtime was able to be 36.4% faster than distro-oriented container images and introduce a small 26.9% overhead over distroless images, both compiled ahead-of-time.

Final considerations

WebAssembly stands out with its significantly faster cold start times compared to container runtimes and much smaller artifact sizes, which are at least an order of magnitude smaller than OCI container images. However, WebAssembly is not yet a complete substitute for container runtimes in serverless environments, as containers continue to offer superior sustained compute performance, essential for more resource-intensive tasks.

By integrating WebAssembly runtimes with the APIs and CLIs of existing container runtimes it is possible to achieve the best of both worlds, while reusing the existing mature tooling and orchestration tools developed primarily for container based workloads. This approach addresses the orchestration challenge for server-side WebAssembly execution without needing entirely new solutions, instead relying on existing components.

